

SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS

GREENE is an EU-funded project focused on pioneering advancements in high-performance permanent magnets, re-engineering their microstructure to make them powerful while at the same time reducing Rare Earth (RE) content. The project is tackling the environmental and supply challenges associated with these crucial components of high-tech products that power a green energy future, such as e-vehicles and wind turbines.

KEY FACTS

€8
Mio
EU-Funding
(Horizon Europe)

15
Partners from 10
European Countries

4
Years
(1st June 2024 until 31st
May 2028)

CONCEPT

Models & Simulation

Optimisation of the grain boundary & production of magnets with enhanced properties and less critical materials

CONSORTIUM

COORDINATOR: Jožef Stefan Institute; Prof. Kristina Žužek

SINGLE-GRAIN RE-ENGINEERED ND-FE-B PERMANENT MAGNETS

GREENE is an EU-funded project aimed at advancing high-performance permanent magnets by redesigning their microstructure. The project focuses on producing powerful magnets while reducing the use of Rare Earth elements, addressing both environmental concerns and supply chain risks. These innovations are critical for enabling the next generation of green technologies, including electric vehicles and wind turbines.

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CONCEPT

A complete value chain

CONSORTIUM

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